

Perception of Non-special Education Teachers Vis-a-Vis Mainstreamed Learners: Stories to Tell

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Abstract. This qualitative study explored the experiences of non-special education (non-SPED) teachers in addressing the challenges of teaching students with disabilities in an online learning environment, focusing on their accountability and coping strategies. Using a phenomenological approach, the study gathered data through semi-structured online interviews with ten participants from the Manay South District, Division of Davao Oriental. The research aimed to understand how non-SPED teachers manage issues such as student tardiness and the difficulties in meeting individual student needs without formal special education training. Analysis revealed three key themes: (1) choosing appropriate strategies and motivating students, (2) identifying individual needs, and (3) the demanding but rewarding nature of their tasks. Teachers coped by exercising patience, receiving help from stakeholders, and relying on parents' commitment and assistance. The findings emphasized the critical role of collaboration between teachers, parents, and the community in supporting students. Additionally, the lack of specialized training for non-SPED teachers contributed to difficulties in addressing diverse learning styles and needs. These insights underscore the necessity for better teacher preparation and strong parent-teacher partnerships in inclusive education.

KEY WORDS

1. mainstreamed learners education 2. non-sp. teachers

Date Received: July 25, 2024 — Date Reviewed: August 01, 2024 — Date Published: September 2, 2024

1. Introduction

Many students with special needs have challenges with independent learning. They often need specialized instruction and more scaffolded support, such as tasks broken down into more manageable chunks, visual aids, and frequent check-ins to ensure they are on the right track. Among the issues raised by non-special education teachers is the lack of pedagogy and didactics to handle learners with learning disabilities in their classes. Lack of such requisite skills is a significant challenge affecting the quality of class instruction. Providing support services from professionals and specialists, parents, volunteers, and peers or buddies to children with special needs is an essential feature of the inclusion program. Parental Involvement. This plays a vital role in preparing the children for academic, moral, and spiritual development. Moreover, this study would navigate the experiences and emotions of non-special education teachers while doing their job as a teacher in special education teachers handling learners with special needs. In the international context, Gregory Chapman, (2013) reported that classrooms

are full of different learners, both culturally and linguistically, in this second decade of the 21st century. Every classroom is diverse, and each one contains unique perspectives and traits of young people eager to learn. Teaching various kids is always a difficult task for any instructor. To meet the requirements of their varied students, teachers must be aware of how their kids learn best (Gregory Chapman, 2013). The task of teaching pupils who have individual characteristics and a range of learning preferences is one that teachers must develop and improve. To assist students in integrating the curriculum's information, teachers should take into account the learners' academic distinctions. In the national scenario, children who struggle to acquire the basic education curriculum and require a modified or functional curriculum and a differentiated special education curriculum to reach their full potential are said to have special educational needs (Heward, 2003). According to Article II, section 17 of the Philippine Constitution, the right to EPA is enshrined in Philippine law. It stipulates that the state shall prioritize education, and Article XIV, section 1 ensures that everyone has access to this education. In the Philippines, several laws about disabled people have been passed, including the RA 7277 or Magna Carta for Impaired Persons and the BP 344 to improve the mobility of disabled people. These laws have been updated to include The Magna Carta for Disabled Persons, which has introduced some rules on special education in the Philippines. The law provides for the rehabilitation, self-development, and self-reliance of disabled persons and their integration into mainstream society. In support to RA 7277, a DepEd Order No. 26, s. 1997, it was issued that all divisions should organize at least one SPED center to cater to children with special needs (DepEd, 1997). Education for All (EFA), a global movement backed by UNESCO that sought to offer top-notch fundamental education to all children, youth, and adults, has been established to give

a more inclusive education. Following the first World Conference on Education for All, held in Jomtien, Thailand, whose slogan was "EFA by the year 2000," international attempts to promote EFA increased (UNESCO, 1990). The importance of Jomtien lies in its recognition of the exclusion of numerous categories of students who are vulnerable and marginalized from educational systems worldwide. It also presented a vision of education as a much broader concept than schooling, beginning with early childhood, emphasizing women's literacy and recognizing the importance of basic literacy skills as part of lifelong learning. This was a landmark conference towards inclusive education, even though this concept was not widely used then. The new method of educating children with different abilities and learning challenges alongside those with average skills is known as inclusive education. All children's learning needs are addressed, focusing on those most at risk of marginalization and exclusion. It indicates that everyone who wants to learn—whether they have disabilities or not—can access standard preschool programs, schools, and community educational settings with suitable support systems. This is possible only in a flexible education system that assimilates the needs of a diverse range of learners and adapts itself to meet these needs. However, despite the continued movement toward inclusive practices in Australia, recent studies overseas have found that many teachers have less than positive attitudes toward students with disabilities and their inclusion in general education classrooms. Teachers set the tone of classrooms, and as such, the success of inclusion may well depend upon the prevailing attitudes of teachers as they interact with students with disabilities in their classrooms (Milton Rohl, 2014). Furthermore, there was a lack of literature showing the actual lived experiences of teachers in the Philippines when it comes to teaching students with disabilities. Similarly, our South District in the Division of

Oriental also has a similar case where many of the teachers who handle special education teachers were specialized in it. For this reason, I, as a researcher, intend to study the challenges experienced by teachers in teaching students with disabilities and their coping mechanisms to address the said challenges. This helped us understand the struggles that special education teachers experience as well as in knowing how they handle them.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore the challenges of non-SPED teachers in teaching special education students and their coping mechanisms to address these challenges. Special education teachers are generally known for managing high-stress levels

and pressure on the job. Therefore, they needed to receive the necessary support and mentorship to show up to work and thrive. So, teaching special education students was a big challenge for non-SPED teachers. In this regard, it was essential to learn and understand the feelings of these teachers tasked to teach special education students because of the lack of teachers to handle the non-availability of items in every school division and the training of teachers.

1.2. Research Questions—The study aimed to investigate the challenges experienced by non-special education teachers and the coping mechanisms used to address them. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences and challenges of Non-Major SPED teachers in dealing with learners with Disability?
- (2) How do non-major teachers in SPED cope with the challenges of teaching learners with disabilities?
- (3) What educational management insights are drawn from the study findings?

In-service teachers are given insight into the challenges non-special education teachers experience and their coping mechanisms to address them. This would give them a deeper understanding of what special education teachers go through teaching special education students. Policy/program implementors could use the results of this study to create policies and programs for teachers that would allow them to help non-teachers better teach special education students. Lastly, this research would help other researchers if they wish to conduct a similar or comparative study.

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following terms were defined conceptually and operationally for better understanding of the readers: Non-Special Education Teacher- A teacher of special education educates students in a way that accommodates their individual differences, disabilities, and special needs. Mainstreamed Learners- Mainstreamed students were part of

the special education classroom. This is considered mainstreaming when they enter the regular education classroom for specific subjects. In comparison, inclusion students are regular classroom students who receive special education services. SPED was an education designed to facilitate the learning of individuals who, for various reasons, require additional support and adaptive pedagogical methods to participate in and meet learning objectives in an educational program. Disability—A learning disability is a reduced intellectual ability and difficulty with everyday activities—for example, household tasks, socializing, or managing money—that affects someone’s whole life.

1.4. Review of Significant Literature—This section reviews key literature on inclusive education and its challenges. Despite global initiatives like the Salamanca Statement (1994) and Education for All (EFA), inclusion remains difficult to implement due to practical, struc-

tural, and cultural barriers (Göransson Nilholm, 2014; Dyson, 2014). Inclusive environments should involve all students, but most studies focus on special needs perspectives, lacking practical evidence for successful inclusive practices.

1.4.1. Non-Special Education Teachers' Encounters—Many children worldwide face discrimination due to disabilities, which hinders their access to education (UNICEF, 2013). Laws like the Magna Carta for Disabled Persons (RA 7277) in the Philippines mandate access to education for all, but implementation remains a challenge (Agaton, 2012; DepEd, 1997). Teachers are often unprepared to teach in inclusive settings (Muega Echavia, 2011), and societal attitudes towards disability also hinder progress (Adjodhia-Andrews, 2007).

1.4.2. Choosing Strategy and Motivation—Special education in online schools has seen growth, offering flexibility for students with disabilities (Beck et al., 2014). However, teachers often lack training in online instruction for special needs students (Ahn, 2011; Basham et al., 2015), and parents must provide significant support at home (Clifford, 2018). Although research on online special education is limited, mixed results indicate a need for further study (Woodworth et al., 2015; Molnar et al., 2019).

1.4.3. Identifying Individual Needs—Special education has evolved from integrated to inclusive models, but barriers persist, especially in developing countries like the Philippines (Sarason, 2015; Dalonos, 2013). Teachers often lack the resources and training necessary for effective inclusion (Gezahegne Yinebeb, 2011). Uganda, for example, faces challenges such as stigma and insufficient funding, which limit the inclusion of children with disabilities (Kristensen et al., 2003).

1.4.4. Patience and Consideration—Inclusive education requires broad participation from society, teachers, and families (Salamanca Statement, 1994). Adjustments in school settings, such as providing Braille materials and teacher

training, are crucial for inclusion (Holbrook, 1996). Positive attitudes from teachers and peers are necessary to foster an inclusive learning environment (Kristensen et al., 2003).

1.4.5. Help from Stakeholders—School-based management (SBM) and parental involvement are vital for improving educational outcomes. Studies show that strong school-home-community relationships lead to better academic achievements (Epstein, 2009; Henderson Mapp, 2002). SBM policies in the Philippines aim to involve stakeholders in continuous school improvement efforts (Abulencia, n.d.; DepEd, 2006).

1.4.6. Parent's Commitment and Assistance—Parental involvement is key to student success. Epstein (2001, 2009) emphasizes the importance of partnerships between schools, families, and communities. Schools with strong parental support see better student outcomes, especially when parents are engaged in decision-making, volunteering, and learning activities at home (Henderson Berla, 1994; Sanders Sheldon, 2009).

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was guided by the constructivist theory, which is grounded in Vygotsky's work (1978). In the constructivist theory, gaining knowledge is an active process in which learners build new constructs, ideas, or concepts centered on their existing and previous knowledge and experiences. In an educational setting, essentially, learning is related to constructivism. During this process, knowledge and teaching are influenced by learning (Abbas, Lai-Mei, Ismail, 2013). The constructivist theory implies that teachers produce knowledge and develop meaning based on their experiences (Gilakjani et al., 2013). In the course of this progression, a variety of diverse teaching practices are utilized, which encourage teachers to use various techniques to stimulate knowledge and to reflect on the learner's current perceptions. In a constructivist learning environment, when teachers use technology as an

instructional tool, the active structure of knowledge is supported (Ertmer et al., 2012). Ermer et al. reported that teachers who incorporated technology as an instructional tool contended that “classroom teaching resources must become an integral part of the learning process”. In turn, it is imperative for teachers to actively use the additional teaching resources to facilitate learning for students with intellectual disabilities. The theoretical frameworks, which guided this study, were based on in the work of Vygotsky’s (1978) social development theory and Piaget’s (1954) cognitive development theory. Vygotsky’s social development theory has influenced methods of teaching and learning in regard to social interaction, which De León (2012) maintained it as an essential component in the development of cognition. Vygotsky (1978) stated that “the most significant moment in the course of intellectual development, which gives birth to the purely human forms of practical and abstract intelligence, occurs when speech and practical activity, two previously completely independent lines of development, converge”. A typical teaching strategy supported by Vygotsky (1978) is recognized as project learning. “Project learning develops an interpersonal connection, which is concentrated on collaborative preparation, and instruction is linked to support learners to develop a meaningful moment to lead to powerful feedback and reflection”. This concept supports teachers in their efforts to produce knowledge and develop the meaning of their role to assist learners and accomplish their learning potential to an intellectual maximum (Gredler, 2012; Joseph Ramani, 2011). In this framework, project learning aligns with Vygotsky’s beliefs related to social relationships and cultural contexts, and the teacher’s role is to structure interactions and develop instruction into achievable steps for the learner. In this teaching strategy, the special education teacher’s experiences are used to engage students, which allows the special education teacher to construct mean-

ing by implementing the iPad as an instructional tool for students with intellectual disabilities to develop a practical understanding of the concept. The zone of proximal development (ZPD) is an essential principle of Vygotsky’s (1978) work. This acronym, ZPD, is identified as the tasks that a learner can perform with the guidance of others (Nyikos Hashimoto, 1997). The ZPD in educational settings is related to the concept of scaffolding. During this process, teachers are accountable for structuring interactions and developing instruction in small steps based on tasks the learner can independently accomplish (Khodamoradi et al., 2013). According to Vygotsky, when students are in the ZPD during learning, the delivery of appropriate assistance will provide students with a boost to achieve the task. The implementation of technology as an instructional tool was described by De León (2012) as a strategy to scaffold learning, which connects to Vygotsky’s (1978; ZPD) concept. Scaffolding is acknowledged as an important learning strategy for yielding learning success. Scaffolding is essential in Vygotsky’s ZPD during the teaching and learning process as it guides knowledge development, a vital growth process. Frederick Taylor’s Scientific Management Theory also called the Classical Management Theory, emphasizes efficiency, much like Max Weber’s. However, according to Taylor, employers should reward workers for increased productivity rather than scolding employees for every minor mistake. Taylor further said that the principal object of management should be to secure the maximum prosperity for the employer, coupled with the maximum prosperity for each employee. In their broad sense, maximum prosperity was used to mean not only significant dividends for the company or owner but the development of every branch of the business to its highest state of excellence so that prosperity may be permanent. Vygotsky’s (1978) concept, more knowledgeable other (MKO), is related to this study in

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

that it refers to the teacher, who has a better understanding or a higher ability level than the learner, regarding a specific task or procedure, or concept (Cicconi, 2013). Vygotsky’s theory is focused on the actual mechanism, which relates to constructivism and identifies mediation as its key proponent. Vygotsky believed that the learning experienced by a student was related to the social interactions with skilled tutors, such as a teacher. Vygotsky points to the role of an MKO in demonstrating technology, concepts, values, and strategies, which learners internalize and learn from a person who has a higher ability level than the learner (Cicconi). Vygotsky identified the MKO concept as a collaborative or cooperative dialogue. These findings infer an alignment with Vygotsky’s ZPD and MKO, which illustrates the gap between human thoughts developed from teachers’ experiences

in implementing the different instructional tools for students with intellectual disabilities. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected working themes. The experienced challenges of special education teachers, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice would enhance this practice and their coping mechanisms to address their challenges. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that exploring special education teachers’ challenges and coping mechanisms was vital to improving the teaching and learning process.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study’s design, identifying the respondents and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI’s growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. The three most common qualitative

methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions of the Study—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Good research-undertaking starts with selecting the topic, problem, area of interest, and paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm is the patterning of a person's thinking; it is a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was submitting to a view (Stanage, 2007). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who define a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action," dealing with first principles, 'ultimates,' or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. In developing research methodologies, three types of philosophical assumptions are being used. Epistemological assumptions deal with subjective evidence that is collected from field studies. Axiological assumptions consider the researcher's biases and actively report them; it was used to establish whether the environment being studied was a product of the behavior encountered or the behavior was a product of the environment (Pring, 2014). Ontological assumptions refer to the nature of the reality of the subject being researched. The latter assumption best suits my study as a qualitative researcher; I believe that different individuals perceive these realities. I also believe that these realities were heavily shaped by their experiences. Using phenomenology as a methodology, this proposed study focuses on the teachers' opinions, feelings, experiences, and inner thoughts concerning their knowledge, values, and skills acquired. It adopts a realistic ontology in which it follows the physical world, where I, as the researcher, assumed the existence of a world of causes and effects. It is not the ontology of mechanical causes caught in the cause-effect relationships; in this study, the researcher assumed that some realities exist in the world and may affect how teachers proceed to the next level. Thus, the researcher that as qualitative researchers follow a realistic ontology, they view it as a casual reality. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation,

thus, multiple realists exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of the implementation of online distance learning modality during the pandemic were elaborated since there were no face-to-face classes. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I ensured that the participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985), as cited by Creswell (2013), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011), I will identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." The purpose of this research was to gather essential details on the learners' experiences with regard to tardiness in these new regular face-to-face classes. I assured them that I would establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences of learners as they went through their teaching activities during the off-classroom classes. Axiology refers to the role of values in research.

Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret them in light of the participants' personal interpretations. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher might write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, using qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study, the researcher used the first person to explain the learners' experiences and coping mechanisms and thoroughly discussed their responses during the interview. As a researcher, I agree with the post-modernism philosophy of Afzal-os-sadat Hossieni (2011). I believe that education aims to teach critical thinking, knowledge production, individual and social identity development, and self-creation. In postmodern education, teachers lead students to discover new things. They provide opportunities to discuss different subjects in creative ways. In this situation, students learn to listen to other voices. They tolerate others' criticism and try to think critically. They learn to respect other cultures and nationalities. Also, they emphasize cooperative learning, independent learning, and dialectic, critical and verbal methods. It was deduced that postmodernism and creativity are embedded in each other, and we could find the result of this opinion in post-modern education.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method, and it was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter. In contrast, the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In

this study, the experiences and coping mechanisms of the physical education teachers, specifically those learners from Lingayao Elementary School, Many South District, Davao Oriental Division, were unleashed from their narratives. The researcher's drive to know the deeper meaning of the predicaments of the non-special education teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". Using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the floating teachers so that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), experience is a source of knowledge that shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap critical insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By using phenomenology, which was concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the teachers' subjective experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms were explored, and insights were drawn as the basis for possible future research and policy analysis about this research.

2.3. Research Design—This study uses a qualitative research design employing a phenomenological approach. According to Han-

cock, et.al (2009), qualitative research answers questions regarding the issues involving societal problems. It raises the question of why people behave as they do, the possible opinions and attitudes formed in a particular situation, how people are affected by society in their ways of action, and how the practices and culture in the society developed. Phenomenology, as a philosophy and a method of inquiry, was not limited to an approach to knowing; instead, it was an intellectual engagement in interpretations and meaning-making used to understand the lived world of human beings at a conscious level. The researcher could adopt interviews, observations, and discussions as data collection strategies within a phenomenological method of inquiry; therefore, phenomenology has both philosophical and methodological stances (Qutoshi, 2018). A phenomenology was described as an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal was to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced regarding the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data is then read, reread, and culled for phrases and themes that are then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon.

2.4. Research Participants—Purposive sampling was applied to the selection of the research participants. Purposive sampling was a

technique in which the researcher relies on judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. It was a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample were chosen by the researcher's judgment. Researchers often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include public school teachers, either male or female, in Lingayao Elementary School, Manay South District, in the Division of Oriental. There were seven informants who was part of the in-depth interview. Moreover, coding was used to protect the participants' identities. IDI-FTA to IDI-FTJ were the roles that helped attain the study's success. First, I asked for permission to conduct the study, which would start with the Schools Division Superintendent and then with my study participants. As a researcher, if consented, I recorded the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview aims to better understand teachers' experiences in the new standard way of teaching and learning. The interview would also include how the Department of Education should improve it was programmed. After the needed data had been gathered, the researcher transcribed and analyzed everything. However, human instruments are more important to study in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions regarding the persons involved in the research (Greenbank, 2003).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection analysis, and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, the researcher would deal with former teachers in public schools and ensure an authentic response from the participants, the researcher was responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants were highly considered. Besides,

they would not be forced to be part of the study when they refuse. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers or aliases can protect the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants were allowed to ask the researcher questions about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information was clear to the participants. Moreover, the participants' data gathering and participation are guided by the Informed Consent Form, which the chosen participants sign. Lastly, the results and findings were presented back to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview were kept private. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This would provide the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information that they feel might identify them. As a researcher, I would reserve the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—As a researcher, I would ensure that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which is the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher would strive to ensure that

the study can be completed successfully at the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for improving the study. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed by the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect to the local traditions, cultures, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study would not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher would necessarily express great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher would respect other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher would ensure that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and or results are included or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.7. Research Instrument—In this study, I used an Interview Guide Question Tool with sub-questions for the virtual in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The tool was used as my guide while interviewing the selected elementary teachers who had been my participants in the recorded virtual in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This aimed to answer the research questions and collect additional inputs that could be used in my study. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically on the method, I asked for help from the experts. My interview guide question tool was checked and validated by the experts. The sampling I

used to select my participants was following the suggestions of the expert panels. In this study, I played various roles to attain the study's success. First, I asked for permission to conduct the study, which would start with the school division Superintendent and then with my study participants. As a researcher, if consented, I recorded the actual interview to achieve the needs of this type of research. The interview aims to better understand teachers' experiences in the new usual way of teaching and learning. The interview would also include how the Department of Education should improve it was programmed. After the needed data had been gathered, the researcher transcribed and analyzed everything. However, human instruments are more important to study in case the quality of this research has to deal with biases and assumptions regarding the persons involved in the research (Greenbank, 2003).

2.8. Data Collection—The researcher secured a letter of permission to the participants. I would use the data collection forms as prescribed in the qualitative design upon approval. Purposive sampling was applied to the selection of the research participants. Purposive sampling was a technique in which a researcher relied on judgment when choosing population members to participate in the study. It was a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample are chosen by the researcher's judgment. Researchers often believe they can obtain a representative sample by using sound judgment, saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include all teachers in Lingayao Elementary School in the Davao Oriental division. Seven informants would participate in the virtual in-depth interview. Moreover, coding was used to protect the participants' identities. IDI-1 to IDI-7 would be used for the informants of the in-depth interview. The researcher needs to understand the subjective interaction between the study participants. Using the interpretive

paradigm, the researcher relied heavily on naturalistic methods such as interviewing and audio recording. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing, observation, and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to construct a meaningful reality collaboratively. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data collection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. To have legitimate and trustworthy data on teachers' experiences of the new normal way of teaching and learning, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. This interview aims to gather information on the feelings and experiences of the Non-Special Education teachers of public schools. The participants were encouraged to express their answers in the most comfortable manner. The interview with the participants has been transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored so that they could be easily found and protected from damage and loss.

2.9. Data Analysis—In analyzing the qualitative data, I used discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Discourse analysis focuses on the language use and patterning of the study's informants, as reflected in the detailed transcripts of recorded speech (Bueno, 2016). I transcribed and analyzed the recorded in-depth interview and focus group discussion. Part of the analysis was to determine female school leaders' challenges, coping mechanisms, and leadership behavior. Thematic analysis was a method of identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns within data (Braun Clarke, 2006). It was a widely used method of analysis in qualitative research. In this study, I looked for patterns and

themes generated in the transcribed in-depth interview and focus group discussion.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The concepts of validity and reliability were relatively foreign to qualitative research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the credibility issue, interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Transferability is concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in demonstrating that the results of the work at hand could be applied to a broader population since the findings of a qualitative project are specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It was impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions apply to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it was my responsibility as a researcher to ensure sufficient contextual transformation about the fieldwork sites to enable the reader to make such a transfer. Confirmability was associated with objectivity in science, which is the use of instruments that are not dependent on human skill and perception. However, it was difficult to ensure real objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires are designed by humans, the intrusion of the researcher's biases was inevitable. Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work's findings were the result of the participants' experiences and ideas rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher.

2.11. Framework for Analysis—In the conduct of this study, I would follow a procedure that will lead to giving answers to the main

Fig. 2. Framework of the Study

questions. The first phase of this study involves collecting data through an in-depth online interview of selected informants through Google Meet or Zoom. After this, the data were organized, transcribed, encoded, and translated. The transcribed data or significant statements that were developed were subjected to data analysis using discourse and thematic analysis or grouped into themes. The analyzed data were thoroughly interpreted by the researcher with the help of the theories of this study. Common themes based on the informants' responses were given utmost consideration in this study. The participants' experiences were described in

the textural description. With the list of non-redundant units of meaning, the researcher must continue to bracket any assumptions to remain true to the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). I rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. Clusters of themes are typically formed by grouping units of meaning together (Creswell, 1998; Moustakas, 1994). Figure 2. shows procedures undertaken to analyze the textual data. Statements were developed from the transcripts and grouped into larger units of information called "meaning tunings" or themes (Creswell, 2007).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from analyzing the interview data. It presents themes that emerged from the analysis. Along with the themes, comprehensive discussions answered the objectives of the study. Before I begin my discussion, I would like to establish the symbols I used to present the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. In reference to the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, I used T01-T12 as codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. Experiences and challenges of non-major sped teachers in dealing with learners with disability—The study's first objective is to

uncover the experiences of non-SPED teachers in dealing with learners with disability. The questions were able to gather substantial actual

experiences from teachers.

3.1.1. Choosing Appropriate Strategy and Motivation—The first theme under the experiences of Non-Major SPED teachers in teaching learners with a disability is that the learner’s motivation is mainly regarded as a central condition for successful learning. However, other factors like intelligence, previous knowledge, and interest also play an important role. In the context of teaching SPED classes, strategies should be considered. Motivation and applicable strategies in teaching are used to activate orientation to a target status, which is regarded as positive in teaching-learning situations (Rheinberg, 2010). Based on the interview, motivation is a driving force to act to achieve something, as articulated by the respondents during the interview. According to T01, the learner’s motivation is mostly regarded as the central condition for successful learning. However, other factors, like status and learning difficulties, may affect the learners’ learning. Hence, the interest among the learners with special needs plays an important role as well. What is problematic about learning and knowledge-gaining processes is integrating strategies in teaching learners with disabilities. It is also hard to introduce new knowledge to them since they have their field of interest (Friedrich Mandl, 2012). Necessarily, a school for learners with special needs must be where students learn how to learn and thus successfully acquire learning strategies. It means that the statements of T01 and T02 contribute to the development of the learners despite their learning disabilities. This corroborates with the study of Aquino et al. (2019) that balance and holistic development of children should be ensured. According to Nachiappan et al. (2018), to overcome the problem of teachers in teaching and learning, practical teachers must have wide knowledge through extensive reading to implement the various activities more interestingly. Moreover, the responses of the key informants supported the study of Tough (2015)

that current pedagogical research focuses on student’s learning processes in general and also on which learning strategies students should be introduced to enable effective learning. Also, T02, one of the key informants mentioned that “Lack of available and updated Teachers guide and curriculum guide and seminars among teachers” is one of the problems she encountered. This means that in the conflict between imparting knowledge and developing the students’ learning competence school education puts the focus on the materials needed in teaching. The study revealed that limited special needs education teachers in the Division of Davao City was a problem. It was found that the special needs education teachers in some schools were not professionally educated. They have limited strategies in dealing with learners with special needs. It was also revealed that the colleges that provide special needs education for teachers were few compared to ordinary education colleges. However, these cannot produce enough teachers to teach special needs education schools in the entire division. Given all the citations and testimonies of the respondents, teaching strategies and motivation are important elements in teaching learners with special needs. Thus, it is important for teachers to examine the learning disabilities among students as early as possible to know what the appropriate strategies and motivations are to be used in teaching

3.1.2. Identifying individual needs—The Second Theme is Recognizing the individual differences of the learners, which is a basic concept when teachers prepare to teach. It is a fundamental assumption of strategic teaching and learning that what we choose to teach in the classroom should be an interaction of what we know about the variables of instruction, learning, achievement, and contextual factors. This assumption has driven our quest as individuals and groups to develop an instructional framework (Jones et al., 2017). In an interview, Teacher Carnation mentioned: “I teach learners

with different disabilities in a day. It is very hard to identify their needs.” It is clearly reflected in the statement of T04 that “. . . teaching learners with special needs is very hard because they have their individual needs.” This means that in handling Learners with Special Needs (LSNs), individual needs must be considered. Fairness treatment should also be given to all the students. This statement supported the result of the study by Evans (2015) that paying attention to the needs of students from diverse groups within your course design, including an equality analysis/impact assessment process in your course development, is a useful way of ensuring that you give due consideration to inclusivity and accessibility. The statement of T05 implies that all teachers need to have the knowledge and a wider understanding of the minimum core elements in order to apply them in planning, delivering, and assessing inclusive teaching and learning and to support learners adequately with their skills in these areas with different learning needs. Developing and improving minimum core skills enables the SPED teacher to consider the best way to teach and support the development of the skills of learners with special needs. Based on the statements of T06, she encountered the same challenges in handling students with disabilities. This means that teachers in SPED encounter difficulties if they have limited skills in handling the students with special needs. Moreover, it is important that teachers especially early childhood educators should understand parental involvement and recognize its positive effects to the teaching and learning process (Bartolome et al., 2020). T07 testified this.

3.1.3. Challenging but fulfilling—this is the third theme Working with special needs students gives you the opportunity to impact the lives of children who have disabilities, learning disorders, and developmental delays. Not only are you making an impact in the lives of students by giving them tools and resources to

learn according to their learning style. Special needs teachers also experience deep, personal fulfillment in knowing that they are shaping a child’s life in a way that will carry beyond their education. Because each student’s unique challenges are unique, special education teachers get to exercise creativity and problem-solving skills more so than in a traditional classroom. The student-centered approach in a special education setting gives a level of autonomy and resourcefulness to meet a variety of learning abilities in a single setting. Douglas and Travers (2012) recognized that IEPs can assist students with special educational needs to gain access to an appropriate education despite their learning disabilities. This means that as a SPED teacher, it is very important to help the students develop their potential despite their learning difficulties. The teacher considers different factors that may help the students grow and enhance their skills if they have. These statements emphasized that as SPED teachers, we need to extend help to the learners with special needs, not for promotion. It also stressed that the teacher’s contribution to the students on how they cope with their learning disabilities is very important. This implies that teachers’ efforts and skills play a very important role in molding and shaping the learners’ abilities and potential in school despite their difficulties. Figure 3 shows the emerging themes from the experiences of non-sped teachers in dealing with learners with disabilities. The first theme that emerged was Choosing Appropriate Strategy and Motivation. According to the teachers, they find it challenging to think and come up with strategies that resonate well with the learners. They make sure that the strategies they use are in line with the learners’ learning styles. The second theme that emerged was identifying individual needs. In respect to their rights to education, the teachers make sure that the learners’ individual needs are being attended to. However, they find it challenging because it is time-consuming and exhausting. With the

Fig. 3. . Experiences of NON-SPED Teachers in dealing with learners with disability already excessive workload, the teachers find it difficult to tailor instruction according to the individual needs of mainstreamed learners. The final theme that emerged was Challenging but Fulfilling. The teachers’ opinions show how big their hearts are. Despite their lack of train-

3.2. *Coping Mechanism of Non-Sped Teachers to Cope with the Challenges of Dealing with Mainstreamed Learners*—Another objective of the study is to explore the different coping mechanism that Non- Major SED teachers may experience From the interviews, the teachers shared that the coping mechanisms they employ are having Patience and Consideration, Help from stakeholders, and Parents’ commitment and assistance.

3.2.1. *Patience and Special Consideration for Children*—When working with children who have special needs, the key instructional strategy for them is to reduce the time pressure associated with tasks. They need more time to learn and practice certain skills. Providing extra time to complete the required task helps mainstreamed children come up with the pressures in a regular classroom setting (Smith Broomhead, 2019) A common belief is that” including” students with disabilities is vitally a matter of making sure that the student” fits in.” Non-SpEd teachers in general education classrooms aim for their mainstreamed students to be well accepted, for them to feel comfortable. One

ing and specialization in teaching mainstreamed children, they bend, compromise, accept, and consider the learners. According to the teachers, it’s more than the reward of promotion; it’s the joy they feel when they teach the children and eventually learn from them.

advantage of inclusion for a special education student is the chance to make a new friend and share new experiences (“ Rationale for and Benefits of Inclusion”). The student is exposed to a whole new sector of the student populace that they are naturally not exposed to in the special education classroom. They can develop which leads to bigger acceptance by their peer in and out of the school community (Correa Wagner, 2011). It is clearly stated based on the statement of T01that “. . . It was very difficult because if I will give feedback and comments on them, their parents will not let their children attend studies anymore. So, acceptance of the parents must be considered” in her line, through the feedbacks and comments of the SPED teachers, parents will be immediately embarrassed. This implies that the value of acceptance must be intensified and the essence of working as a team or partner in helping the students to be fully developed shall be considered. Additionally, acceptance must be given value in handling SPED classes. Teachers and parents discussed the consequences and other significances if the parents refused to accept the learning disabil-

ities of their children. As one of the SPED teacher Carnation confirmed that: “Our school head, some of my co-teachers and parents are very supportive to the special education program. But, based on my challenges, some of the parents are deniable; they refuse to accept the reality that their children have learning difficulties. In this case, as a special education teacher, you need to be patient and considerate.” It is clearly reflected in the statement of Teacher Carnation that “. . . some of the parents are deniable, they refused to accept the reality that their children have learning difficulties.” in her line, there are still parents who never accept the situation of their children with learning disabilities. This implies that even the school head and other teachers extend support to the SPED program if parents refuse to accept the reality, the ultimate goal of the SPED program will not be realized. Inclusive education has been widely recognized and developed by a number of international normative instruments elaborated by the United Nations; thus, education is not a privilege. It is a human right (Matkoba, 2018). The statement of T02 implies that in the country the right of the students to access quality education shall be given to them regardless of their status. It is essential to help students with disabilities to access education with the help of teachers. This is being supported that, the state shall protect and promote the right of all the citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all (Article XIV, Section 1). Moreover, it is very important to consider the rights of the learners. This was stressed out by Yusof and Ismail (2020) that the acceptance of special needs children in private and public kindergartens is under consideration and following the rules and regulations. Also, despite the insufficient resources and other materials in teaching students with disabilities, the teacher finds possible ways to teach them. The teacher can modify some parts of the curriculum in the regular classes to

fit the curriculum of the SPED classes.

3.2.2. *Help from Stakeholder*—Education is made feasible in many contexts with the ongoing assistance of the stakeholders, as stated in the Department’s Mission Statement, “Family, community, and other stakeholders are actively involved in generating lifelong learners.” To create effective education systems and effective learning environments, all stakeholders need to come together in a meaningful way through collaboration and, therefore, connection. Successful collaboration between all stakeholders means deep listening as well as active doing. Open, transparent dialogue results in all parties feeling seen, heard, and valued, and in the end, it’s the connection and compassion formed through those healthy relationships that create successful teaching and learning outcomes. Education is made feasible in many contexts with the ongoing assistance of the stakeholders, as stated in the Department’s Mission Statement, “Family, community, and other stakeholders are actively involved in generating lifelong learners.” To create effective education systems and effective learning environments, all stakeholders need to come together in a meaningful way through collaboration and, therefore, connection. Successful collaboration between all stakeholders means deep listening as well as active doing. Open, transparent dialogue results in all parties feeling seen, heard, and valued, and in the end, it’s the connection and compassion formed through those healthy relationships that create successful teaching and learning outcomes.

3.2.3. *Parent’s commitment and assistance*—Teachers and principals often count on parents to help them create a positive learning environment in their schools. The family-school partnership can take the form of parents discussing education matters with their child, helping with homework, supervising their child’s progress through education, communicating with school personnel, participating in decision-

Fig. 4. How non-sped teachers cope with the challenges in dealing with mainstreamed learners

making, and being involved in school activities (LaRocque et al., 2011). The first three forms of parental involvement entail interactions between parents and their children; they are referred to as home-based parental involvement. The latter three require interactions between parents and the school staff; these are collectively referred to as school-based parental involvement. This chapter examines primarily three forms of school-based parental involvement that are essential for creating a positive school climate: communicating with teachers, volunteering in school-related activities, and participating in school governance (Cohen et al., 2009). Parental involvement refers to parents' participation in their children's education at home and school. This can take many forms, such as helping with homework, attending school events and parent-teacher conferences, participating in decision-making processes, or regularly communicating with the child's teacher. Parental involvement is a critical factor in the success of children's education. When parents are in-

involved in their children's education, children are more likely to do well in school and have better social and emotional development. Getting involved at school allows parents to obtain first-hand information on the learning environment, learn how to navigate the education system, demonstrate to their child that education is important, and influence their child's behavior by establishing consistent norms (Cohen et al., 2009) Previous studies have found that parental involvement in their child's education has a positive effect on student outcomes (Castro et al., 2015) even if the effect is largely dependent on the quality of this involvement (Borgonovi Montt, 2012). The constructive involvement of parents in school activities has been positively associated with, among other things, student achievement (Haynes, 2012), social skills (Sheridan et al., 2012), attendance (Aviate et al., 2014), good behavior (Domina, 2005; Sheridan et al., 2017), positive relationships with school-mates (Garbacz et al., 2018) and mental health (Wang Sheikh-Khalil, 2014).

Figure 4 shows the emerging themes in how the teachers cope with the challenges in dealing with learners with special needs. The first theme that emerged was Patience and Consideration. Teachers believe that it is important to deal with

these learners with empathy. According to the teachers, they give ample consideration to these learners and also extend their patience in teaching them. The second emerging theme is Help from Stakeholders. As the teachers have re-

sponded, it is a great help that they get support from their PTA and the LGU. According to the teachers, they feel valued that the stakeholders are concerned and participating in their cause. The third emerging theme is Commitment and Assistance from Parents. The teachers have opined that it is very helpful that parents are assisting their children at home and that they have good communication. In education, it is very necessary that the teacher and parents share the same vision

3.3. *Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study*—Based on the findings of the research study, several conclusions were drawn. First, most teachers teaching children with learning disabilities did not receive any special needs education training from the school, they feel that they are not qualified to teach children with learning disabilities. Moreover, teachers assigned to SPED classes lack strategies for dealing with learners with disabilities. Second, this study revealed that the classrooms for children with learning disabilities in the Division of Davao Oriental at large have poor learning environments to support the SPED such as a lack of budget, curriculum guide, Instructional Materials (IMs), and even school facilities. Third, it could be concluded that placing learners with special needs in an inclusive classroom with ordinary learners is not enough without proper support. Fourth, learners with disabilities did not receive all the necessary support and services to access the curriculum facilities. Fifth, stakeholders' support is very minimal to support the needs of the students enrolled in SPED classes. On the other hand, issues and problems were solved technically to sustain a positive working environment among school heads, teachers, and stakeholders. In light of the findings and conclusions drawn from the results of

the study, the Department of Education should continue strengthening the implementation of SPED in different schools through the following recommendations. First, the Department of Education Training and Development, in collaboration with regional in-service officers, should organize continuous professional development opportunities on inclusion strategies for learners with SPED needs. In addition, workshops should equip teachers with practical skills in instruction, collaboration, alternative forms of evaluation, classroom management, and conflict resolution, and how to adapt the curriculum. At the same time, the teachers' initial training programs should incorporate inclusive education components. Second, provisions of human and material resources are also important for the implementation of SPED needs. The Department of Education should provide more adequate resources, equipment, and teaching material for learners with diverse learning needs. Third, teachers handling SPED classes are not trained in the area of Special Needs Education. Therefore, these teachers are failing to support learners with learning disabilities adequately. The Department of Education should recruit trained teachers, and those who are not trained should be trained through in-service training. Fourth, proper placement of the students with learning disabilities shall be done. The implementers of the SPED programs shall strictly adhere to the policies. Fifth, the strong support of the stakeholders shall be encouraged by formulating an active organization spearheaded by the school head. Sixth, future research in this area should involve systematic development work across a range of sites and settings, which also allows for the examination of the impact of the innovations upon achievement.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study and its implications based on its findings. This study aimed to uncover the experiences of non-SpEd teachers in dealing with mainstreamed learners. This paper utilized a phenomenological study, which was purposively sampled by 21 non-SpEd teachers who best met the study's purpose. The data gathered were analyzed through thematic analysis. The first theme that emerged was Choosing Appropriate Strategy and Motivation. According to the teachers, they find it challenging to think of and devise strategies that resonate well with the learners. Therefore, they made sure that the strategies they used were in line with the learners' learning styles. The second theme that emerged was identifying individual needs. Regarding their rights to education, the teachers ensured that the learners' individual needs were being attended to. However, they found it challenging because it was time-consuming and exhausting. With the already excessive workload, the teachers find it difficult to tailor instruction according to the individual needs of mainstreamed learners. The final theme that emerged was Challenging but Fulfilling. The teachers' opinions show how big their hearts are. Despite their lack of training and specialization in teaching mainstreamed children, they bend, compromise, accept, and consider the learners. According to the teachers, it's more than the reward of promotion; it's the joy they feel when they teach the children and eventually learn from them. The second objective was to discover the coping practices of the non-SPED teachers in dealing with learners with special needs. The first theme that emerged was Patience and Consideration. Teachers believed that it was important to deal with these learners with empathy; they considered these learners and also extended their patience in teaching them. The second emerging theme was Help from Stakeholders. As the teachers have responded, it was very helpful that they get support from their PTA and the LGU. According to the teachers, they feel valued that the stakeholders were concerned and participating in their cause. The third emerging theme is Commitment and parental Assistance. Teachers have opined that it was very helpful that parents assist their children at home and that they communicate well. In education, it was necessary for teachers and parents to share the same vision.

4.1. Implications—The purpose of this study was to investigate and narrate non-SpEd teachers' inclusive education practices for mainstreamed children with special needs. Based on the analysis conveyed it could be concluded that non-SpEd teachers employed common yet fundamental inclusive education practices in handling mainstreamed children with special needs. However, these practices revealed that non-SpEd teachers were commonly addressing the behavior aspect of the mainstreamed children, and only a few employed practices that would cater to their social and cognitive aspects of development. Therefore, non-SpEd teachers can somehow cater to the needs of their mainstreamed learners despite the lack of expertise in handling children with special needs. Hence, it was necessary to upskill non-SpEd teachers with appropriate inclusive education practices to cater to children with diverse needs. The results have shown that non-SPED teachers are having a lot of challenges specially in the pedagogical areas of teaching learners with special needs. Since Non-SPED teachers did not undergo training to teach these learners, they are having a hard time on teaching strategies and with learners learning styles and individual needs. This implied a need for more schools that offer special education. The results of the study also implied that there were some SPED

teachers who are satisfied in teaching students with learning disabilities. In this belief, understanding learning disabilities or challenges that may impede a student's ability to learn was vital to providing the best possible classroom environment. Students with learning disabilities are no less intelligent than the average student and often require very simple accommodations to maximize their learning experience.

4.1.1. Future Directions—The research study was limited by its qualitative nature and by the research methodology itself. Due to the variables concerned, objectivity was often an important issue because the researcher interprets the data based on her understanding of the descriptions, perceptions, and insights provided by the 21 non-SpEd teachers. The researcher learns and analyzes the data concerning the 21 non-SpEd teachers' experiences through her lens. The research findings would likely contribute to the research literature and inform and inspire all other non-SpEd teachers in public and private schools. School Heads: It may be helpful to conduct a similar study on a broader scale to sum up the teachers' challenges in a whole District for broader implementation of possible solutions in addressing them. Similar and comparative studies can also be done for this study as findings can vary with a different population. School Heads can focus on providing professional development opportunities for non-SPED teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in supporting students with diverse learning needs. Training programs, workshops, and seminars can address specific areas, such as inclusive teaching strategies, classroom man-

agement techniques, and differentiation strategies. Teachers: Teachers may work together to foster an inclusive school culture that values and celebrates diversity. This may involve implementing policies that promote inclusion, creating supportive environments that encourage collaboration and respect, and implementing awareness campaigns to challenge stereotypes and biases. Learners: Learners play a crucial role in promoting inclusive education. By actively participating and challenging any negative perceptions towards non-SPED teachers, they can make a significant impact. Initiatives such as awareness campaigns, peer support groups, and inclusive classroom projects can empower students, giving them a sense of responsibility and the opportunity to advocate for a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Future Researchers: The role of future researchers in advancing the field of inclusive education is crucial. By conducting studies to investigate the attitudes and perceptions of non-SPED teachers towards inclusive education, they can provide valuable insights. These insights can identify areas for improvement and propose strategies to enhance the understanding and effectiveness of teaching students with diverse needs, thereby contributing significantly to the field. By focusing on these future directions, School Heads, Teachers, Learners, and Future Researchers can contribute to creating a more inclusive educational system where non-SPED teachers are well-equipped, valued, and supported in their efforts to meet the diverse needs of all students.

5. References

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